

MEDALS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: ABOUT THE AWARDEES

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ANNOTATION

In this scientific article, the medals, which are of special importance in awarding the services of citizens to the state and the people in independent Uzbekistan, and the contribution of those awarded with this award to the development of the country's economic, social, and cultural spheres, are described through the legal basis. Also, special attention was paid to the description of these established medals, their differences and similarities, to whom they are awarded, for what services, awarding procedures, prize money, and the statistics of those awarded over the years. .

Keywords: *state award, medal, badge, "Courage", "For loyal services", "Fame", "Builder of the future", "Healthy life", awarding.*

INTRODUCTION. Medals are also of special importance in the system of state awards of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the years after independence, a number of medals were established in our country, and awarding works were carried out with them in the past period. In the years of independence, medals such as "Courage", "For Loyal Services", "Fame", "Builder of the Future", "Healthy Life" were established.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Methods and methods such as objectivity, truthfulness, idealism, patriotism, historicity, statistical comparative analysis are used in this scientific article. Given that it is related to the period of independence and that it is being researched for the first time, information on the subject is recorded mainly in periodicals and collections of laws. In particular, a number of awards are introduced by relevant laws in different years. If we analyze the issues of awarding the awardees, according to the events of awarding awards to 748 awardees on the occasion of the 14th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 60 candidates will be in the Oksaroy residence, 3 in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, 6 in the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 2 Awarding of the remaining candidates in the Cabinet of Ministers in regions, ministries, committees and organizations has been determined [1.64.].

RESULTS. Awarding the "Courage" medal to the people who showed bravery and selflessness in the way of protecting the peace of our country, military servicemen for their bravery and bravery in the performance of their duty has become important. On May 5, 1994, the "Courage" medal was established [2.1.]. With this medal, military personnel of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Security Service, the National Guard and the employees

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of the internal affairs bodies have shown courage and bravery in ensuring the national security of the republic, maintaining public order and fighting crime, during the performance of military duty or service duty. are rewarded for. Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan or non-citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with the "Courage" medal for their bravery in maintaining public order, saving people's lives, state and public property during natural disasters, fires and other emergency situations. possible Awardees will receive a one-time monetary award in the amount of ten times the base calculation amount, and the medal will be worn on the left side of the chest [3.19.]. The medal is made of 0.5 micron thick copper alloy over 0.25 micron gold plated nickel and has a diameter of 34 millimeters in a circle. The obverse of the medal, covered with air-colored enamel, depicts an equestrian warrior holding a shield and sword, symbolizing glory and valor, against a background of sun and radiating rays. In the lower part of the medal, the inscription "Courage" is given. The national coat of arms is depicted on the back of the medal[4.85.]. "Courage" medal, author of the picture, A. Mamajonov. The chairman of the National Security Service, G. Aliyev, was awarded with this medal in 1994 for his effective work in the long-term system. In 2007, the promoter of "Yuniversum" company - Klaus Peter Kohl will be awarded for his great contribution to the development of Uzbek professional sports and for supporting young athletes in every way. By 2021, a total of 2,036 people have been awarded this medal.

On July 6, 2007, the law on the medal "For Loyal Services" was adopted. Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who have demonstrated their high professional skills, loyalty to military and patriotic duty with the "For Loyal Services" medal, strengthen the country's defense capability and national security, increase the combat readiness of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and ensure law and order in Uzbekistan. are rewarded for their great service in their work, and in some cases, persons who are not citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are also awarded and receive a one-time monetary reward in the amount of ten times the base calculation amount. The medal is worn on the left side of the chest and is made of 0.25 micron gold-plated copper alloy and has a diameter of 34 millimeters. On the obverse side of the medal is an image of a serviceman on a background of an eight-pointed star in a circle. At the top of the medal, the words "For Loyal Services" are written in a circle. The lower part of the medal features an eight-pointed star and laurel leaves around the circle. The state coat of arms is depicted on the back of the medal, the number of the medal is written at the bottom [5.27-29.]. For the first time in 2007, 25 law enforcement officers were awarded with this medal[6.100-102.]. A total of 816 persons were awarded until 2021.

The Medal of the Creator of the Future was established by the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017. With this medal, those who demonstrate the qualities of patriotism, selflessness and hard work, who faithfully serve the interests of the people, who make a worthy contribution to raising the prestige and glory of our country in the international arena, who are active and proactive in the social and political life of our country Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who are an example to their peers and who have made great

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achievements in their studies and work, who have reached the age of 14 and are not older than 30, will be awarded and a one-time payment in the amount of ten times the amount of the base calculation will receive the award. The medal is worn on the left side of the chest, its structure is made of a copper alloy with a thickness of 0.5 microns nickel and then a thickness of 0.25 microns gold, and it is circular in shape. On the front side of the medal, in the center, on a white background, there is a symbolic image of the atom of peace, which is a symbol of modern scientific and technical progress, the globe, its meridians and parallels, a map of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as an image of two palms, which are symbols of support. At the top of the medal, the words "Builder of the Future" are written in a circle. In the lower part of the medal there are two olive branches in a circle, in the center of which there is a crescent and a star, and the edges are surrounded by a blue border. The state coat of arms is depicted on the back of the medal, and the medal number is written at the bottom [7.17-19.]. 9 women were awarded this medal for the first time in 2021 [8.114-115.]. 19 persons were awarded with this medal in 2021.

DISCUSSION. Among the existing medals in our republic, the Medal of Fame is distinguished by the fact that it has been awarded the most. With this medal, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and non-citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have achieved great success with their honest work in the development of the economy, science and culture of the republic, and in the work of educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism and loyalty to the ideas of national independence and social development individuals are rewarded and receive a lump sum of five times the base calculation amount. The medal is worn on the left side of the chest[9.20-21.]. It is made of copper alloy with a thickness of 0.5 microns nickel, and then with a thickness of 0.25 microns. On the obverse side of the medal, a scene symbolizing the economic power of Uzbekistan is depicted in the rays of the rising sun. In its lower part, the inscription "Shuhrat" is written, and the state emblem is depicted on the back. The number of the medal is written on the lower part and worn with a clasp[10.92.]. The author of the image of the "Fame" medal is A. Mamajonov. From the establishment of the medal to 2021, 8582 persons were awarded. In particular, in 1994, 3 employees of the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine[11.7], a famous French scientist, a brilliant scholar of the history of Timur and the Timurids, Lucien Keren, who is passionate about bringing the societies of Uzbekistan and France closer together, were among the first to be awarded this medal. 12.78.]. In 1996, Lee Kwan Ki, President of DEU and Chairman of UzDEU, was awarded for his great achievements in the construction of the joint venture "UzDEU" in Asaka[13.3.]. In 2006, on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the establishment of the Pakhtakor football team, 20 athletes and coaches who set a special example in the development of football in Uzbekistan were awarded, 12 of them were deceased athletes (R.Agishev, An Mikhail, O.Ashirov, S. Bazarov, K. Bakanov, Sh. Ishbutayev, G. Krasnitsky, Kh. Rakhmatullayev, V. Sabirov, I. Tazitdinov, M. Talibdjanov, V. Fyodorov). In 2007, Muhamad Khamam Al-Abdullah, the President of the Asian Football Confederation, 14 parents over one hundred years old, who have worked honestly for the development of our country, and who have been making a great contribution to the

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education of young people with their advice, one person will be awarded from the territorial unit.

On May 26, 2020, the Law on the "Healthy Life" medal was adopted. With this medal, doctors of health care institutions, media representatives covering a healthy lifestyle, heads of sports schools, general education schools and pre-school educational institutions for their significant contribution to the formation of healthy lifestyle skills, sports trainers, for their outstanding services in raising the feelings of patriotism, love and loyalty to the Motherland in young people through sports competitions - representatives of the defense system, mayors and their deputies, heads of physical education and sports organizations, sponsors, attached to sports federations (associations) heads of enterprises and organizations are awarded.

Individuals awarded with the medal receive a one-time monetary award of ten times the base calculation amount and it is worn on the left side of the chest. The medal is made of 0.25 micron gold-plated copper alloy and has a diameter of 34 millimeters. In the lower part of the front of the medal, there is a globe with a map of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in its upper part there is a symbolic image of a healthy family against the background of the rising sun. Along the circumference of the medal is the inscription "Healthy Life", and in the lower part there are two laurel branches attached to an eight-pointed star. The national coat of arms is depicted on the back of the medal and the medal number is printed in the lower part. The thickness of the medal is 3 millimeters, and the edges of the front and back sides are surrounded by a bubble circle. The medal is attached to a green silk ribbon-covered five-pointed pin with a hook and loop. The width of the tape is 24 millimeters, the width of the white borders is 1 millimeter. On the back of the pin there is a device in the form of a stud for attaching the medal to clothing [14.29-32]. For the first time, 4 women were awarded with this medal by the decree of March 4, 2021 [15.114.]. 11 persons were awarded with this medal in 2021.

CONCLUSION. It should be said that in the years after independence, a number of medals were established in our country, and awarding works are being carried out until now. Unlike other awards, it is distinguished by the small number of medals. The medals are similar in appearance, distinguished by the images in the center of the medal, and different compositions are used based on the name of each medal. In addition, it should be mentioned that jubilee medals dedicated to different dates were also established.

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